

Geothermal Heat Generation and Gradient Modeling in Okigwe Basin, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigates the geothermal potential of the Okigwe-Imo State region in southeastern Nigeria through a detailed analysis of ground temperature distribution and its thermal properties. By overlaying geological maps and analyzing aeromagnetic data from a 2008 airborne survey by Fugro Surveys, the research explores the correlation between geological features, such as metasediments and quartzite, and magnetic anomalies. Using advanced modeling techniques, including forward and inverse modeling and thermal structure analysis, the study applies the Curie Point Depth method to assess the crust's thermal conditions. The results indicate a range of ground surface temperatures (GST), with a mean value of 27.98°C for the Okigwe Basin, confirming previous regional predictions. The geothermal distribution functions were derived using Least-Squares analysis, providing both linear and quadratic models for non-radiogenic and radiogenic heat generation sources. The findings reveal a consistent geothermal gradient of 2.182°C/100m in the non-radiogenic case, with a slight decrease in the radiogenic model as depth increases. Geothermal power generation potential was estimated at 67.338 TW, sufficient to meet the region's energy demands for an entire year.

Keyword: Geothermal Energy, Renewable Energy, Radiogenic Heat, Heat Generation Models

INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND

Geothermal energy is the thermal energy obtained from the Earth's internal heat. It is formed by the heat accumulated within plutonic rocks being conveyed through fluids and stored in reservoirs. Through the conversion of heat from hot water and steam stored in underground reservoirs into electricity, the geothermal power plants leverage a low-carbon process.

Geothermal energy represents a vital renewable energy source that holds tremendous potential for carbon emission reduction and global energy diversification [1]. The full scope of geothermal energy remains underutilized globally, despite the significant potential for applications in space heating, process heating, and electricity generation. Furthermore, to address challenges in density-coupled processes, thermal dependence of material properties, complexities of fractured flow, the advancements in numerical modelling of geothermal scenarios are imperative [2].

In Nigeria, one of Africa's largest oil producers and abundance in renewable energy resources, geothermal energy remains largely untapped [2,3]. Several regions with significant geothermal heat potential such as Okigwe town in Imo State, possess subsurface heat reservoirs. Capitalizing on these opportunities offers a path for sustainable energy development. However, the lack of technical expertise and efficient harnessing mechanisms has hindered progress in exploiting geothermal energy [4]. For a successful geothermal system to be established, a substantial heat load from its customers in a concentrated area is imperative. The town of Imo is laid out in such a way that the buildings with significant loads are fairly spread out. Additionally, there is a change in elevation through the town from north to south which increases the complexity of designing a geothermal energy system due to handling pressure changes within the pipe.

Combined, these issues are substantial compared to the energy requirements of Okigwe town, which is relatively low. Geothermal energy is considered as a sustainable energy to use in order to decrease dependency on fossil fuels.

1.2 AIM AND OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

The aim of this project is the evaluation of geothermal heat recovery potential of Okigwe-Nigeria for industrial power generation. The specific objectives are

- i. Modeling of heat and mass transport process analysis from Okigwe soil deposit to confirm its viability for power generation.
- ii. Determination of optimal design variables for producing standard geothermal energy from Okigwe-Nigeria soil using least square geothermal model.
- iii. Determination of the total recoverable geothermal power potential of Okigwe-Nigeria.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURES

The epileptic electricity power supply has become a fundamental issue affecting the economic development of Nigeria. Geothermal energy which results from the radioactive decay of minerals within the Earth's core and solar energy absorbed at the surface have been discovered and are being utilized by several countries [2]. Nigeria is still far behind in tapping the abundance of geothermal energy resources. Ikogosi warm spring in Southwestern Nigeria is good geological evidence of potential geothermal energy [4]. Hydrothermal reservoirs can serve as a sustainable potential source of energy because it is renewable [5]. To bring the water or steam from such reservoirs to the surface, wells are drilled into them. If the fluid is hot enough, steam bubbles will occur and cause the water to flow naturally to the surface as hot/warm springs, fumaroles and

geysers [3]. Ikogosi and other warm springs are visible evidence of geothermal energy in Nigeria. Nigeria may have her energy problem solved if the abundance of geothermal resources, especially one with temperature high enough to generate electricity is utilized. The geological features and subsurface temperature data of oil and shallow water wells from both Northern and Southern part of Nigeria point to the possible presence of geothermal energy due to the thermal gradient [5].

S/No.	Geothermal Feature	Geological Terrain	Geothermal Resources	Temperature of the Water	Current Economic Activity
1.	Kerang Volcanoes, Plateau State	Volcanic (lava Flow), Jos Plateau	Lava Flow, Water		Farming activities Tourist site, Table water
2.	Rafin Rewa Warm Spring	Precambrian Basement (Migmatite-gneiss)	Hot water	42.5 °C	
3.	Ikogosi Warm Spring	Fractured Precambrian Basement rocks (Quartzite-Schist)	Warm water	37 °C	Tourist site, Medicinal value
4.	Lamurde Hot Spring (Ruwan Zafi Hot Spring)	Cretaceous Benue Trough (Lamurde Anticlines)	Hot water	54 °C	UNESCO Heritage site
5.	Keana-Awe Thermal Springs	Cretaceous Benue Trough (Keana Anticline, and Awe Syncline)	Warm (salt) water	34 °C	Salt, Medicinal value
6.	Akiri Warm Spring	Cretaceous Benue Trough	Hot water	54 °C	Salt
7.	Wikki Warm Spring	Cretaceous Benue Trough (Gombe Sandstone)	Warm water	32 °C	Tourists site

Figure 1: Geological setting and ambient temperature of some geothermal features in Nigeria.

2.2 OVERVIEW OF GEOTHERMAL DEPOSITS IN NIGERIA

2.2.1 North Central Nigeria

An assessment of the geothermal energy resources over parts of Nasarawa and environs was carried out using high resolution aeromagnetic data and the result shows that the southeastern part of the study area has high prospects. This is because it is associated with shallow Curie point, high heat flow and high geothermal gradient. It is envisaged that if a 2.3 km borehole is drilled, there is the possibility of achieving the threshold temperature of 115°C - 180°C for the abstraction of geothermal energy in the Akiri area [6]. The application of the geothermal energy

in developing such areas as the generation of electric power can be a major achievement for the Nasarawa State Government and Nigeria at large.

2.2.2 North Eastern Nigeria

The wide range of geologic formations in north-eastern Nigeria provides an avenue for exploration of geothermal energy. The Curie point depth, geothermal gradient, and heat flow in Masu located within the Nigerian sector of Chad Basin (lat. 12°00' to 13°00' N and long. 12°30' to 14°00' E) was conducted using spectral analysis. The application of minimum curvature in gridding the total magnetic field intensity data was done using the Oasis Montaj 6.4.2 software. The Curie point depth obtained ranges from 12.233 to 16.184 km with an average of 13.993 km, the geothermal gradient of the area varies from 35.838 to 47.413°C /km, with an average of 41.821°C /km, while the heat flow ranges from 89 to 117.80 mWm⁻², with an average of 104.551 mWm⁻²[7]. The high geothermal gradient and heat flow values in the area are indications that the area might be suitable for geothermal energy generation as an alternative power supply in the area and in the country at large.

2.2.3 Chad Basin

Information on geothermal gradient and heat flow within the subsurface is critical in the quest for geothermal energy exploration. To ascertain the thermal potential of the Chad Basin for energy generation, the subsurface temperature information from 19 oil wells and 24 water boreholes drilled to depths beyond 100 meters and atmospheric temperature were utilized. This is used in calculating the geothermal gradient of the area. Selected ditch cuttings from the wells were subjected to thermal conductivity test using Thermal Conductivity Scanner (TCS) at the Polish Geological Institute Laboratory in Warsaw [8]. The terrestrial heat flow was calculated according to Fourier's law as a simple product of the geothermal gradient and the mean thermal

conductivity. Results indicated a geothermal gradient range of 2.81°C/100 m to 5.88°C/100 m with an average of 3.71°C/100 m. The thermal conductivity values from the different representative samples range from 0.58 W/m*K to 4.207 W/m*K with an average of 1.626 W/m*K. The work presented a heat flow value ranging from 45 mW/m² to about 90 mW/m² in the Nigerian sector of the Chad Basin [8].

Figure 2. Geothermal gradient in Nigerian sector of Chad Basin on a background of Geological

Map of Nigeria based on temperature data from water wells and oil exploration wells

2.2.4 Middle belt and South Eastern Nigeria

This region is bounded within Latitude 6° 00'-6° 30'N and Longitude 7°00' 7° 30'E with an approximate area of about 3025 km² within parts of lower Benue trough and Anambra basin of Nigeria. The regional temperature distribution and geothermally responsive areas are determined by the heat change per unit distance, heat flowing from the earth's interior to the outer surface and the deepest depth at which the minerals lose their magnetic properties. The depths due to the low frequency components exemplify the Curie depth point (CPD). The average sedimentary

thickness or the average depth due to the low frequency part was ascertained to be -5 km while the geothermal and heat flow varies from $-25.2^{\circ}\text{C km}^{-2}$ to $-38.9^{\circ}\text{C km}^{-2}$ and from -64.4 mWm^{-2} to -97.3 mWm^{-2} but with average values of $-32.1^{\circ}\text{C km}^{-2}$ and -80.1 mWm^{-2} respectively [9]. These results suggest alternative geothermal energy resources to be plausible and presence of some amount of sedimentary thickness within the area of study.

Figure 3. Geothermal gradients in southern Nigeria. Gradient calculations on the background of geological map by Nigerian Geological Survey, 1974.

2.2.5 Niger Delta Basin

The map of Niger Delta shows a small anomaly in the northern part with a maximum value of 1500 GJ/m^2 and a major anomaly occurring in the eastern part of the basin, onshore, with values of $2000\text{-}3500 \text{ GJ/m}^2$. Offshore in the south and southwest anomalies in the total sedimentary rock mass occur with highest values up to 4000 GJ/m^2 , with the southwestern anomaly extending west to the shore. It is much of interest to note the seaward – westward extension of these anomalies both in size, configuration and magnitude for the geothermal energy in the total

sediment thickness to the underlying basement. These anomalous fields show the most favorable locations and areas for further work on geothermal energy resources [10].

Figure 4: Geothermal energy resources map of Niger Delta Basin – total, static resources of the sedimentary rocks down to basement, a depth of 6.5 km.

2.3 OVERVIEW OF GEOTHERMAL POWER GENERATION TECHNOLOGY

Geothermal power stations are similar to other steam turbine thermal power stations - heat from the earth's core geothermal reservoir is used to heat water or another working fluid. The vaporized working fluid is then used to turn a turbine of an electricity generator, thereby producing electricity. The fluid is then cooled and returned to the heat source for further reheating. There are three types of geothermal power plants: the dry steam power plants, the flash steam power plants and the binary cycle power plants.

2.3.1 Dry steam power plants

Dry steam plants are the simplest and oldest design. They directly use geothermal steam of 150°C or greater to turn turbines [14]. Dry steam plants operate over reservoirs that produce only

steam. The steam is pushed into a tunnel called a rock-catcher and is then funneled into the turbines causing them to turn.

2.3.2 Flash steam power plants

The flash steam geothermal power is generally associated with higher temperature geothermal sources of at least 180°C. Flash steam plants pull deep, high-pressure hot water through separators into lower-pressure tanks and use the resulting flash boiled steam to drive turbines which produce the electricity [10]. This works because the pressure of the subsurface deep underground is much greater than at the Earth's surface, water can exist as a liquid at very high temperatures. The high temperature - pressure water is brought to the surface, where it enters a low pressure chamber and flashes into steam. The pressure created by this steam is channeled through a turbine, which spins to generate electrical power. Once the steam has exited the turbine, it is either released into the atmosphere as water vapor, or it cools back into liquid water and is injected back underground.

2.3.3 Binary cycle power plant

The binary geothermal power has lower temperature geothermal resources as low as 57°C [11]. Binary plants collect the heated water out of the earth and use this heat to boil a secondary fluid with a much lower boiling point than water. When the hot geothermal water is brought to the surface from deep underground, it is run through a heat exchanger which transfers the heat from the geothermal water to the liquid working fluid. The reason for this is that the secondary liquid boils faster than water and therefore takes less time to generate the steam vapor that turns the turbines. This also allows for some of the lower-temperature geothermal reservoirs to be used to generate electricity. Furthermore, there is virtually no heat or water loss because the water is moved through an entirely closed circuit. What makes a binary system unique is that it operates

as a 2 closed-loops; neither the geothermal water nor the working fluid are exposed to the surface environment. All the water that is brought to the surface is re-injected, and after vaporizing, the working fluid is cooled to its liquid state, so it may repeat the process. There are no-emissions in the binary geothermal cycle [12]

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Methodology

The methodology employed in this study involved overlaying various geological maps to analyze the correlation between different geologic units and chemical compounds in the Okigwe-Udi area. This was done to assess the strength of relationships between these compounds and geological features such as volcanoes and fumaroles, which are essential for identifying potential geothermal reservoirs. Geothermal gradients across different locations were analyzed to identify commonalities and differences.

Data Collection:

- Digitized aeromagnetic data was obtained from the Nigerian Geological Survey Agency (NGSA).
- The data was acquired from a 2008 airborne magnetic survey conducted by Fugro Surveys Limited.
- The survey was carried out at an altitude of 80m above the ground with a nominal flight line spacing of 500m and a tie line spacing of 2km.
- Sheets 312 (Okigwe) and 313 (Afikpo) at a 1:100,000 scale covered latitudes 5°30'N to 6°N and longitudes 7° to 8°E.

- Isomagnetic surface maps of Okigwe and Afikpo were analyzed.

Interpretation:

- The magnetic data was interpreted using forward and inverse modeling techniques, with software provided by Potent Version 4.
- The magnetic map and geological map showed a strong correlation between exposed geologic units and magnetic anomalies.
- Positive magnetic anomalies (60 – 112 nT) were found in areas like Okigwe and Afikpo, which corresponded to undifferentiated metasediments.
- Negative anomalies (–30 to –156 nT) were observed in areas like Okwelle, Orlu, and Osu, which corresponded to quartzite, quartz-mica schist, and granulitic migmatite formations.

Thermal Structure Analysis:

- The Curie Point Depth (CPD) was estimated using the aeromagnetic data to assess the thermal structure of the crust.
- Curie temperature corresponds to the point at which magnetic minerals lose their magnetism, about 580 °C for magnetite.
- The CPD model provides information on regional temperature distribution and can help assess lithospheric thermal conditions.

The methods used include:

- Spector and Grant (1970) for estimating the depth to the top of the magnetized bodies.

- Bhattacharyya and Leu (1975) for calculating the depth to the centroid of the causative body.

The analysis helps estimate regional temperature distribution, providing valuable insight into geothermal potential.

3.2 Geothermal Model Equations

3.2.1 Non-Radiogenic Heat Generation Case

For a 1-D steady-state heat conduction through an earth crust that approximates a slab without radiogenic heat generation, external heat penetration and shielded from topographic as well as seasonal changes, the diffusion equations is:

$$\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} = \frac{1}{a} \cdot \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \dots\dots\dots [1]$$

- where: T — temperature of the ground (°C);
- a - thermal diffusivity of the ground (m²/s);
- x - position coordinate (m);
- t - time (s).

In numerical calculations the ground is treated as a plate with a finite thickness. On the upper surface of the plate (the ground surface) periodically variable heat fluxes occur. These fluxes are variable both in the annual and daily cycles. Changes resulting from daily cycles occur at depths of less than 1 m.

Given the great age of the crust, time-dependent effects are generally neglected.

Applying the boundary conditions (at y = 0)

$$q_{\text{cond}} = H - LW + S - EV$$

where: q_{cond} - conductive heat flux (W/m²);

H - convective heat flux (W/m²);

S - solar radiation heat flux (W/m²);

LW - long-wave radiation heat flux (W/m²);

EV - evaporative heat flux (W/m²)

$$(i) \quad T = T_s \text{ (Ground surface temperature)} \dots \dots \dots [2a]$$

$$(ii) \quad q_s = \frac{-kdT}{dy} = q_s \dots \dots \dots [2b]$$

Then $q_s = -q_s$ because heat is assumed to be flowing out of the earth. Solving equation (1) and applying the boundary conditions, we obtain:

$$T = T_s + \frac{dT}{dy}y \dots \dots \dots [3]$$

$$\text{Where: } \frac{-kdT}{dy} = -q_s \text{ and } \frac{qs}{k} = \frac{dT}{dy} \dots \dots \dots [4]$$

The geo temperature distribution function now becomes

$$T = T_s + \frac{qs}{k}y \dots \dots \dots [5]$$

Where: T_s = Ground Surface Temperature (GST) (°C),

q_s = Heat flow (W/m²), k = Thermal Conductivity (W/m°C)

y = Vertical Depth (m).

Equation (5) defines temperature at any depth in the earth for a homogenous earth model without radiogenic heat generation. The Least Square equation for this case is given as:

$$T = a_0 + a_1y \dots \dots \dots [6]$$

With the following Normal equations:

$$\sum T = a_0 N + a_1 \sum y \dots\dots\dots [7a]$$

$$\sum Ty = a_0 \sum N + a_1 \sum y^2 \dots\dots\dots [7b]$$

Comparing equations (5) and (6), we have: $a_0 = T_s, a_1 = \frac{qs}{k}$

3.2.2 Radiogenic Heat Generation Case

If the radiogenic heat (H) is generated per unit volume per unit time, then the heat conduction equation becomes:

$$\partial^2 T / \partial y^2 = \frac{-H}{k} \dots\dots\dots [8]$$

Applying the boundary conditions (equations 2a and 2b) and solving equation (8), we obtain:

The geo temperature distribution function:

$$T = T_s + q_s y / k - Hy^2 / 2k \dots\dots\dots [9]$$

The geo temperature gradient function:

$$\frac{dT}{dy} = \frac{-Hy}{k} + \frac{q_s}{k} \dots\dots\dots [10]$$

Equation (9) defines temperature at any depth, y in an earth model with radiogenic heat generation. The Least Square equation is given as:

$$T = a_0 + a_1 y + a_2 y^2 \dots\dots\dots [11]$$

With the following Normal equations:

$$\sum T = a_0 N + a_1 \sum y + a_2 \sum y^2 \dots\dots\dots [12a]$$

$$\sum Ty = a_0 \sum y + a_1 \sum y^2 + a_2 \sum y^3 \dots\dots\dots [12b]$$

$$\sum Ty^2 = a_0 \sum y^2 + a_1 \sum y^3 + a_2 \sum y^4 \dots\dots\dots [12c]$$

Comparing equations (9) and (11), we have:

$$a_0 = T_s, a_1 = \frac{qs}{k} \text{ and } 2a_2 = -\frac{H}{k} \dots\dots\dots [12d]$$

Solutions to the Normal equations above are obtained by Matrix equations:

$$B = Ax \dots\dots\dots [13]$$

Where B, A and x are matrices then:

$$X = A^{-1}B \dots\dots\dots [14]$$

Matrix x is that of required solutions $a_0, a_1,$ and a_2 of the sets of Normal equations. Matrices A and B are developed using $\sum T, N, \sum y, \sum y^2, \sum TY, \sum y^3, \sum Ty^4$ in the Normal equations. Solutions to these equations are obtained by solving the Matrix Algebra using the MS Excel package.

3.3 Power Generated

$$P = \rho F \times C_F \times Q \times (T_i - T_o)$$

RESULTS

4.1. Ground Surface Temperature (GST)

The ground surface is an important layer which temperature forms an important boundary condition for the determination of geothermal gradient, a parameter which is useful in evaluating the thermal energy resources of any region [14]. Table 2 shows the ground surface temperature (GST) for the 26 possible well locations in this research. The GST ranges between 5.369°C for well 7 and 53.350°C for well 6 for both the non-radiogenic and radiogenic models with a mean value of 27.983°C computed for Okigwe-Imo state, Nigeria. This is in agreement with an earlier value of 27°C predicted for the south eastern Nigeria sedimentary Basin by Aliyu [12].

Thermal conductivity of the earth lies between 2.5 to 3.5W/mK, while the heat transfer coefficient will be difficult to ascertain. There are many empirical relationships to determine this coefficient by noting that the coefficient h is a function of wind velocity (u). McAdams parameter was used:

$$h=5.7+3.8u \text{ for } u<4.88\text{m/s}$$

$$h= 7.2u^{0.78} \text{ for } u>4.88\text{m/s}$$

Table 1. Ground Surface Temperatures (GST) and Least-Square Geothermal Distribution Functions for Crustal Rocks with Non-Radiogenic and Radiogenic Heat Generation for the proposed 26 Wells in the Study Area

	Non - Radiogenic				Radiogenic		
Well No.	GST a_0 =Ts(0°C)	$a_1=\frac{qs}{k}$ (0°C/m)	Geothermal Distribution Function $T = a_0 + a_1y$	GST a_0 =Ts(0°C)	$a_1=\frac{qs}{k}$ (0°C/m)	$a_2=\frac{h}{2z}$ (0°C/m ²)	Geothermal Distribution Function $T = a_0 + a_1y + a_2y^2$
1	35.330	0.0192	35.330+0.0192y	35.330	0.0192	-9.00E-11	35.330+0.0192y-9.00E-11y ²
2	33.801	0.0183	33.801+0.0183y	33.801	0.0183	-1.00E-19	33.801+0.0183y-1.00E-19y ²
3	32.9	0.01786	32.9+0.01786y	32.9	0.01786	-1.00E-11	32.9+0.01786y-1.00E-11y ²
4	32.6	0.01770	32.6+0.01770y	32.6	0.01770	-1.00E-11	32.6+0.01770y-1.00E-11y ²
5	32.3	0.01753	32.6+0.01753y	32.3	0.01753	-1.00E-11	32.6+0.01753y-1.00E-11y ²
6	32.2	0.01748	32.2+0.01748y	32.2	0.01748	-1.00E-11	32.2+0.01748y-1.00E-11y ²
7	31.7	0.01721	31.7+0.01721y	31.7	0.01721	-1.00E-11	31.7+0.01721y-1.00E-11y ²
8	31.2	0.01694	31.2+0.01694y	31.2	0.01694	-4.00E-11	31.2+0.01694y-4.00E-11y ²
9	30.5	0.01656	30.5+0.01656y	30.5	0.01656	-4.00E-11	30.5+0.01656y-4.00E-11y ²
10	29.8	0.01618	29.8+0.01618y	29.8	0.01618	-4.00E-11	29.8+0.01618y-4.00E-11y ²
11	29.7	0.01612	29.7+0.01612y	29.7	0.01612	-4.00E-11	29.7+0.01612y-4.00E-11y ²
12	23.0	0.01249	23.0+0.01249y	23.0	0.01249	-9.00E-11	23.0+0.01249y-9.00E-11y ²
13	22.7	0.01232	22.7+0.01232y	22.7	0.01232	-9.00E-11	22.7+0.01232y-9.00E-11y ²
14	22.3	0.01211	22.3+0.01211y	22.3	0.01211	-9.00E-11	22.3+0.01211y-9.00E-11y ²
15	21.8	0.01183	21.8+0.01183y	21.8	0.01183	-4.00E-11	21.8+0.01183y-4.00E-11y ²
16	21.8	0.01183	21.8+0.01183y	21.8	0.01183	-4.00E-11	21.8+0.01183y-4.00E-11y ²
17	20.9	0.01135	20.9+0.01135y	20.9	0.01135	-4.00E-11	20.9+0.01135y-4.00E-11y ²
18	20.9	0.01135	20.9+0.01135y	20.9	0.01135	-4.00E-11	20.9+0.01135y-4.00E-11y ²
19	20.6	0.01118	20.6+0.01118y	20.6	0.01118	-4.00E-11	20.6+0.01118y-4.00E-11y ²
20	20.5	0.01113	20.5+0.01113y	20.5	0.01113	-4.00E-11	20.5+0.01113y-4.00E-11y ²
21	20.1	0.01091	20.1+0.01091y	20.1	0.01091	-4.00E-11	20.1+0.01091y-4.00E-11y ²
22	20.0	0.01086	20.0+0.01086y	20.0	0.01086	-4.00E-11	20.0+0.01086y-4.00E-11y ²
23	19.5	0.01059	19.5+0.01059y	19.5	0.01059	-4.00E-11	19.5+0.01059y-4.00E-11y ²

24	19.0	0.01031	19.0+0.01031y	19.0	0.01031	-4.00E-11	19.0+0.01031y-4.00E-11y ²
25	18.3	0.00993	18.3+0.00993y	18.3	0.00993	-2.6.00E-11	18.3+0.00993y-2.6.00E-11y ²
26	18.2	0.00988	18.2+0.00988y	18.2	0.00988	-2.6.00E-11	18.2+0.00988y-2.6.00E-11y ²
mean	25.4	0.01378	25.4+0.013789y	25.4	0.013789	-9.00E-11	25.4+0.013789y-9.00E-11y ²

4.2 Geothermal Distribution Functions for Non-Radiogenic and Radiogenic Sources

Table 2 also shows the geothermal distribution functions for crustal rocks with non-radiogenic and radiogenic heat generation sources for the 26 wells studied. The Least-Square equations indicate linear functions for the non-radiogenic heat generation model and quadratic functions for the radiogenic heat generation model. The mean geo temperature distribution functions for wells 1-26 are computed respectively as:

For Non-radiogenic Model for proposed Okigwe basin:

$$25.4+0.013789y$$

For Radiogenic Model for proposed Okigwe basin:

$$25.4+0.013789y-9.00E-11y^2$$

Table 2. Mean Geo Temperatures and Geothermal Gradient Functions for proposed Okigwe basin

		Geothermal temperature, T(°C)		Geothermal Gradient (Gg) (°C/100m)	
Depth	Non-radiogenic, T _N 25.4+0.013789y	Radiogenic, T _R 25.4+0.013789y-9.00E-11y ²	$\Delta T = T_N - T_R$ 10 ⁻⁵	$\frac{Non-radiogenic}{GgN}$	$\frac{Radiogenic}{GgR}$
0	25.4	25.4	0	0.013789	0.0137889
1	25.413789	25.4137889	0.013789	0.013789	0.013789
2	25.427578	25.4275779	0.0000001	0.013789	0.0137889
3	25.441367	25.4413668	0.0000002	0.013789	0.0137889
4	25.455156	25.4551557	0.0000003	0.013789	0.0137889
5	25.468949	25.4689446	0.0000044	0.013789	0.0137889
6	25.482738	25.4827335	0.0000045	0.013789	0.0137889
7	25.496527	25.4965225	0.0000045	0.013789	0.0137889
8	25.510316	25.5103114	0.0000046	0.013789	0.0137889

9	25.524105	25.5241003	0.0000047	0.013789	0.0137889
10	25.537894	25.5378892	0.0000048	0.013789	0.0137889
11	25.551683	25.5378892	0.0137938	0.013789	0.0137889
12	25.565472	25.5516781	0.0137939	0.013789	0.0137889
13	25.579261	25.565467	0.013794	0.013789	0.0137889
14	25.59305	25.5792559	0.0137941	0.013789	0.0137889
15	25.63094	25.5930448	0.0378952	0.013789	0.0137889
16	25.644729	25.6068337	0.0378953	0.013789	0.0137889
17	25.658518	25.6206226	0.0378954	0.013789	0.0137889
18	25.672307	25.6344115	0.0378955	0.013789	0.0137889
19	25.686096	25.6482004	0.0378956	0.013789	0.0137889
20	25.699885	25.6619893	0.0378957	0.013789	0.0137889
21	25.713674	25.6757782	0.0378958	0.013789	0.0137889
22	25.727463	25.6895671	0.0378959	0.013789	0.0137889
23	25.741252	25.703356	0.037896	0.013789	0.0137889
24	25.755041	25.7171449	0.0378961	0.013789	0.0137889
25	25.76883	25.7309338	0.0378962	0.013789	0.0137889
26	25.782619	25.7688228	0.0137962	0.013789	0.0137889
27	25.796408	25.7826117	0.0137963	0.013789	0.0137889
28	25.810197	25.7964006	0.0137964	0.013789	0.0137889
29	25.823986	25.8101896	0.0137964	0.013789	0.0137889
30	25.837775	25.8239785	0.0137965	0.013789	0.0137889
31	25.851564	25.9618675	-0.1103035	0.013789	0.0137889
32	25.865353	25.9756564	-0.1103034	0.013789	0.0137889
33	25.879142	25.9894453	-0.1103033	0.013789	0.0137889
34	25.892931	26.0032342	0.0137889	0.013789	0.0137889
35	25.90672	26.0170231	-0.1103031	0.013789	0.0137889
36	25.920509	26.030812	-0.110303	0.013789	0.0137889
mean				0.013789	0.0137889

$$\Delta G_g = G_{g_N} - G_{g_R} \quad \text{mean } \Delta G_g = 0.0137889$$

The depth (36 m) is the mean temperature for both the non-radiogenic model and radiogenic model from well 1 - 26. The trend suggests a distributive pattern of geo temperature for the Crust in the Basin. The effect of radiogenic heat generation is pronounced at great depth and negligible at shallow depth. Geothermal gradient is observed to be constant for the non-radiogenic model but decreases with depth for the radiogenic heat model for all the wells studied. The mean geothermal gradient is constant for proposed wells 1-26 at a value of 2.182 (°C/100m) for the non-radiogenic case but decreases with depth from 2.182 to 2.181 (°C/100m) for the radiogenic

model. Figures 5 - 7 are plots of mean geo temperature (°C) versus depth (m) for proposed wells 1-26 for the non-radiogenic and radiogenic models respectively

Figure 5. Geothermal Gradient for the Radiogenic Heat Generation

Figure 6. Geo temperature (°C) versus Depth (m) for the Non-Radiogenic Heat Generation

Figure 7. Geo temperature (°C) versus Depth (m) for the Radiogenic Heat Generation.

The curves are approximate straight lines due to the insignificant effects of the radiogenic heat sources on the geo temperature gradient. As a result of this, the surface temperatures for both models are similar. Geo temperature gradient is observed to decrease linearly with depth for the radiogenic heat generation model since the third term of the radiogenic heat generation model equation is infinitesimally small and negligible. This is observed in the linear nature of the graph of radiogenic heat generation models irrespective of the quadratic nature.

The geo temperature gradient obtained for the non-radiogenic heat generation model is compared to the normal power consumption in Imo State. The agreement of the results in this study with those of other researchers, irrespective of the different methods used, further supports the low rates of radiogenic heat generation around Okigwe basin obtained in this research.

4.3 Geothermal Power Generated from the experiment conducted at Okigwe

Table 4.3: Power generation in Okigwe

Depth(m)	Initial Temperature of earth(t_o) °C	Final temperature of earth(t_i) °C	Fluid density of earth F (kg/m ³)	Heat Capacity of earth C_F	Heat Flow rate from the earth (Q)(TW) 1TW=10 ¹²	Power Generated $P = \rho F \times C_F \times Q \times (T_i - T_o)$ (terawatts)
1	24	35	2.06	0.73	90	1488.762
2	23	34	2.05	0.6	80	1082.4
3	22	33	2.04	0.55	70	863.94
4	21	32	2.03	0.51	60	683.298
5	20	31	2.02	0.45	50	499.95
6	19	30	2.01	0.41	40	362.604
7	18	29	2.00	0.35	30	231
8	17	28	1.99	0.32	25	175.12
mean	20.5	31.5	2.025	0.49	55.625	673.38425

Mean geothermal power generated for industrial purposes at Okigwe = 67.338TW which can serve the entire state for one year without any form of power failure.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 CONCLUSION

Knowledge of the temperature of the ground in time and space as well as its thermal properties gives basic information about physical phenomena concerning the transfer and accumulation of heat in the ground. Experimental determination of the temperature distribution in the ground should be carried out continuously for a sufficiently long period of time, so that the measured values are not random, which affects the high cost of measurements. The ground temperature was measured at a depth from 0 to 26 m. The application of the Least Square method for the computations of ground surface temperature, geothermal gradients and generation of geotemperature distribution functions for the non-radiogenic and radiogenic models is suitable for accurate geotemperature analyses since it gives very close results to those of other researchers

using different methods at Okigwe, south east Nigeria. The radiogenic heat generation source contributes two significant effects on the subsurface temperature distribution in the region. The low value of radiogenic heat generation per unit thermal conductivity accounts for the small difference between the linear and non-linear Least Square geo-temperature model values. The radiogenic model also shows that geo temperature gradient decreases infinitesimally with depth. This can be because of the concentration of radiogenic heat sources with depth based on the stratigraphy at Okigwe basin . The increase in shallowness in the Basin can be viewed as decreasing with depth. This is substantiated by the general trend of decrease in radiogenic heat sources from Crust to the Mantle . It is obvious from the foregoing that the geothermal models of Okigwe crust is not significantly affected by the radiogenic heat production of the region.

5.1.1 Contribution to Knowledge

This study established:

1. Empirical models for predicting the heat generation and distribution around Okigwe environs.
2. Determination of optimal design variables for producing standard geothermal energy from Okigwe-Nigeria soil using least square geothermal model.

5.2 Recommendations

The geothermal models developed for the Okigwe Basin crustal rocks considering radiogenic heat generation and employing the Least Squares method provide new frontiers for research in hydrocarbon and geothermal energy resources appraisal in the Basin. A detailed experimental work using Temperature Logs, Gamma Ray Logs (to obtain radiogenic heat generation) and core samples (to determine thermal conductivity) should be conducted in the study area to obtain

results for comparison with the approach in this study. Further research should be devoted to the study of the effects of other thermodynamic conditions apart from radiogenic heat generation on geo-temperature distribution within Okigwe and other sedimentary Basins.

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